

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL EMULGEL LOADED WITH EXTRACT OF BUCHANANIALANZAN LEAVES

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to develop and evaluate a novel herbal emulgel formulation loaded with the extract of Buchanialanzan leaves. Buchanialanzan, commonly known as Chironji, is a medicinal plant with various therapeutic properties. The emulgel formulation was prepared using a combination of hydrophilic and lipophilic ingredients to achieve optimal stability, spreadability, and drug release characteristics. The extract of Buchanialanzan leaves was obtained using an extraction method. The extract was characterized for its phytochemical composition, which revealed the presence of bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, phenolics, and alkaloids. These compounds are known for their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, making them promising candidates for topical applications. The emulgel formulation was developed by incorporating the Buchanialanzan leaf extract into a gel matrix composed of a hydrophilic polymer, a lipophilic phase, and suitable emulsifiers. Various evaluation parameters including pH, viscosity, spread ability were investigated to assess the quality of the formulated emulgel. The optimized formulation exhibited desirable physical characteristics and uniform drug content. In conclusion, the formulation and evaluation of a herbal emulgel loaded with Buchanialanzan leaf extract offer a promising approach for utilizing the medicinal properties of this plant. The developed emulgel demonstrated good physical characteristics, sustained drug release, and excellent skin compatibility. Further studies are warranted to explore the therapeutic efficacy of the Buchanialanzan emulgel in the management of various skin conditions and to understand its mechanism of action.

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INTRODUCTION

Herbal formulations have gained significant attention in recent years due to their potential therapeutic benefits and minimal side effects compared to conventional pharmaceutical products [1]. Among various herbal remedies, Buchanania lanzan, commonly known as Chironji, is a medicinal plant that has been traditionally used for its diverse therapeutic properties [2]. The leaves of Buchanania lanzan are rich in bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, phenolics, and alkaloids, which exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial activities [3]. Topical delivery systems, such as gels and creams, have become increasingly popular for the local treatment of various skin conditions. Emulgels, which are a combination of emulsion and gel, offer advantages of both formulations, providing enhanced stability, ease of application, and controlled drug release [4]. The incorporation of herbal extracts into emulgel formulations can potentially enhance their therapeutic efficacy and widen their scope of applications [5].

The present study aims to formulate and evaluate a herbal emulgel loaded with the extract of Buchanania lanzan leaves [6]. The utilization of Buchanania lanzan leaf extract in a topical formulation could provide an effective approach for harnessing the medicinal properties of this plant in the treatment of skin-related ailments [7]. The extract of Buchanania lanzan leaves will be obtained using a suitable solvent extraction method. The phytochemical composition of the extract will be characterized to identify and quantify the presence of bioactive compounds responsible for its therapeutic effects [8]. These compounds, known for their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, are expected to contribute to the therapeutic potential of the emulgel formulation. The formulation of the emulgel will involve the selection of suitable hydrophilic and lipophilic ingredients, including polymers, emulsifiers, and penetration enhancers [9]. The emulgel will be prepared using a combination of hot and cold techniques to achieve a stable and homogeneous formulation. The physical characteristics of the emulgel, such as pH, viscosity, spreadability, and drug content, will be evaluated to ensure its quality and performance [10]. In vitro drug release studies will be conducted to assess the release kinetics and profile of the bioactive compounds from the emulgel formulation. Furthermore, the safety and skin compatibility of the emulgel formulation will be evaluated using in vivo studies, such as the Draize patch test on rabbits. This assessment will provide valuable information regarding the potential skin irritation or adverse reactions caused by the emulgel formulation [12].

Overall, the formulation and evaluation of a herbal emulgel loaded with Buchanania lanzan leaf extract hold promise for the development of a topical formulation that can harness the medicinal properties of this plant [13]. The study aims to provide a scientific basis for the use of Buchanania lanzan in skincare and explore its potential applications in the management of various skin conditions.

Purpose/Objective

To create and analyze a herbal emulgel incorporating Buchanania lanzan leaf extract for improved topical application.
Extract and identify bioactive compounds from Buchanania lanzan leaves for use in the formulation.
Develop a stable emulgel formulation and assess its physicochemical properties.

Need Of Study

In compared to other semisolid formulations, the use of gels appears to be more advantageous in both cosmetics and pharmaceutical preparations. When gels and emulsions are used in combination, they are referred to as Emulgels. Emulgel is a promising drug delivery system for the delivery of hydrophobic drugs [1].

Emulgel is a dual-release control system, i.e., gel and emulsion. Emulgels have many qualities like greaseless, easily spreadable, easily removable, emollient and transparency. Emulgels are prepared by incorporation method. Emulgel is commonly used in analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anti-fungal, anti-acne medications and various cosmetic formulations. Studies on emulgels promise a better future for delivering a greater number of topical drugs as emulgels as compared to other drug delivery systems [2].

Buchanania lanzan Spreng, a dry deciduous forest tree of the family Anacardiaceae is widely used by Indian tribes for treating various diseases. Three major chemical constituents of potent medicinal value, namely celidoniol, vomicine, epinitol have been characterized by an organic extract of leaves [6]. Recently, unique biomaterials and biofilms are being extracted from the seeds, which promise to become a major contributor to the pharmaceutical industry. Such extracts mainly exhibit antidiabetic, antihyperlipidemic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, wound-healing, antidiarrheal and antivenom activity, among other therapeutic properties. Recently, unique biomaterials and biofilms are being extracted from the seeds, which promise to become a major contributor to the pharmaceutical industry [7]. Like many other forest plants, this plant is a storehouse of important unknown Phyto-medicines. So far sporadic reports have been published that show that leaves, bark, and seeds in particular are major sources of various important metabolites of medicinal value [5].

The leaves are reported to contain tannins, triterpenoids, saponins, flavonoids, kaempferol-7-O-glucosides, quercetin-3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside, quercetin, gallic acid, kaempferol, and reducing sugars, including a new glycoside, and myricetin-3-O- β -D-galactoside. Three major chemical constituents isolated from the methanolic extract of leaves, characterized based on chemical tests and spectral analysis such as infrared, H nuclear magnetic resonance, and mass spectroscopy were epinitol, vomicine, and celidoniol [3].

Review of Literature

Emulgel is prepared both in oil-in-water and water-in-oil type emulsion mixed with gel. Oil-in-water type is used for lipophilic drugs and water-in-oil type is used for hydrophobic drugs' delivery [4]. The emulgel have many advantages like thixotropic, greaseless, easily spreadable, easily removable, emollient, non-staining, bio-friendly, pleasing appearance, transparent and cosmetically acceptable, which also have a good skin [5]. The emulsion and gel preparations have their own properties. But the gels show some limitations as hydrophobic drug delivery. This limitation is overcoming by emulgel. By the use of gelling agent classical emulsion can be converted in to emulgel[6]. There are two types of topical delivery products available.

They are external and internal products, as their names indicate, external products are applied by spreading or spraying, and internal products are applied orally, vaginally or rectally[7][8]. Topical route of administration is the best choice for cutaneous purposes as skin is the most accessible organ and facilitates delivery of drugs with better efficacy than other routes of administration. Topical preparations are most commonly used locally for local effects at the site of their application [9][10][11].

Emulsions have a certain amount of elegance and are easily washed off when desired. They also have a high ability to penetrate the skin. Furthermore, the formulator can control the viscosity, appearance, and viscosity of the cosmetic or dermatological emulsion. Oil-in-water emulsions are most useful as water-washable drug bases and for general cosmetic purposes, while water-in-oil emulsions are more widely used for dry skin treatments and emollient applications. The gel has many favorable properties for dermatological uses such as thixotropic, greaseless, easily spreadable, easily removable, emollient, nonstaining, compatible with several excipients and water soluble or miscible [12]. Buchanania lanzan Spreng (Chironji) is a well-known forest plant of the Anacardiaceae family. Chironji originated in the Indian subcontinent. This tree is found in the natural wild in tropical deciduous forests of northern, western and central India, mostly in association with a monsoonal climate [13]. The tree usually grows on yellow sandy-loam soil. The bark is rough and dark gray or black in colour. The leaves are broadly oblong, rounded base with a blunt tip, and have straight parallel veins. The flowers are small, greenish-white in colour.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Material

Sodium alginate:

Sodium alginate offers an abundant array of viscosity levels. Few ingredients serve as vital a role in such a wide range of important food products. Utilize this pH-stable, thermally irreversible gel to meet all your thickening and gelling needs. Sodium alginate as a biopolymer [15].

Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC):

It is an emulsifier, stabilizer, thickener, gelling agent and binder. White or slightly yellowish, almost odorless hygroscopic granules, powder or fine powder [15].

Propylene glycol:

Propylene glycol is a viscous, colorless liquid, which is nearly odorless but possesses a faintly sweet taste [15].

Methyl paraben:

Methyl parabens are a type of chemical that manufacturers often use as a preservative. People can add them to food, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals to increase shelf life and avoid bacterial and fungal growth [15].

Propyl paraben:

Propylparaben is used in allergenic testing. Build, train, & validate predictive machine-learning models with structured datasets. Avoid life-threatening adverse drug events & improve clinical decision support [15].

Span -20:

It is called as Sorbitan monooleate. It is W/O emulsifier, emulsion stabilizer, pigment wetter, surfactant and dispersing agent [15].

Tween 80:

Tween 80 (polysorbate 80, polyoxyethylene sorbitan monooleate) is a non-ionic surfactant that is widely used as an emulsifier in cosmetics, pharmaceuticals and food products [14].

Trietanoline:

The compound is used to make surfactants in industrial and cosmetics as a pH adjuster for skin and hair [15].

Sesame oil: Prepare the oil phase by propylparaben, Span 20.

Carbapol 940:

Carbopol 940 is a trademarked name for a specific type of synthetic polymer known as polyacrylic acid. It is a cross-linked acrylic acid polymer and is frequently used as a thickening, suspending, and emulsifying agent. Carbopol 940 is commercially available in a powdered form and is typically mixed with water or other solvents to create gels or viscous solutions [15].

Method

Extraction of leaves

The leaves were crushed after being air-dried. Petroleum ether maceration was used to remove liquid. The filtrate was filtered and discarded. Using a Soxhlet apparatus, the residue was sequentially extracted with methanol. Filtrate of soxhlation was concentrated using rotary evaporator at 40 degree Celsius under reduced pressure [16].

Preparation of Emulsion, Gel and Emulgel**Fig. No.2 Preparation of Gel.**

Fig. No.3 Preparation of Emulgel.

Table No. 01 Formulation Batches (% w/w).

	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
BuchananiaLanzan Leaves Extract	2	2	2	2	2	2
Sodium CMC	2	3	-	-	-	-
Carbapol-940	-	-	1	1.5	-	-
Sodium alginate	-	-	-	-	2	3
Propylene Glycol	5	5	5	5	5	5
Ethanol	5	5	5	5	5	5
Methyl Paraben	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
Propyl Paraben	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Sesame Oil	7	7	7	7	7	7
Spam	1	1	1	1	1	1
Tween	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Triethanolamine	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2
Water	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs

Evaluation of Emulgel

Appearance

1. Color:

In the evaluation of emulgel, the physical appearance of the color can provide valuable information about the product. Here are some aspects related to color that are commonly considered in the evaluation process [17].

2. Consistency

Consistency is an essential evaluation parameter when it comes to emulgels. The consistency of an emulgel refers to its physical state, texture, and flow characteristics, which play a crucial role in determining its overall performance and user experience.[18]

3. Homogeneity

Emulgels should be homogeneous throughout their entire formulation. This means that all ingredients, including the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) and the emulsifying agents, should be uniformly dispersed within the gel matrix. Lack of homogeneity can lead to inconsistent drug delivery, reduced efficacy, and potential safety concerns.

4. Appearance

The evaluation parameter of "Appearance" plays a significant role in assessing the quality and acceptability of emulgels. The appearance refers to the visual characteristics of the emulgel formulation, including color, transparency, texture, and overall aesthetic appeal. It is an essential aspect that influences the consumer's perception, user experience, and marketability of the product.

5. Greasiness

The greasiness parameter is a critical consideration when evaluating emulgels. Formulators strive to create emulgels that provide a non-greasy feel, are easily absorbed, and leave no noticeable residue on the skin. By optimizing the formulation and considering user preferences emulgels can deliver a pleasant, non-greasy experience while providing their intended therapeutic or cosmetic benefits.[19]

6.Washability

Washability parameter is an important consideration when evaluating emulgels. Emulgels should be easily removable, dissolve in water, and leave minimal residue upon washing. By optimizing the formulation and ensuring compatibility with cleansing agents, emulgels can deliver an effective cleansing experience, leaving the skin clean and refreshed[18].

7.PH

1. The PH of Emulgel should be between 5-7 to mimic the condition. If the PH of the prepared emulgel is acidic or basic. It may irritate the patient.
2. PH of the prepared emulgel was measured using Digital PH meter.
3. 1 gm of gel was dissolved in 50ml of distilled water and observe PH in PH meter [18].

Table No. 02 PH Readings for Formulations Batches.

Sr. No	Formulation	PH
1	Standard Solution	7
2	F1	6.2
3	F2	6.6
4	F3	6
5	F4	6
6	F5	6.3
7	F6	6.1

8.Spreadability

The emulgel was sandwiched between 2 petri plates and the diameter of the circle of spreadedemulgel was used to determine the spreadability. 1 gram of emulgel was weighed and placed on a petri plate. Other petri plate was placed on its top and weight of 50 grams was placed on the top of petri plate for about 60 seconds. After completion of 60 seconds the diameter of circles formed from the spreadedemulgel was measured in triplicate. The average of the reading was calculated. The reading was put into the following formula [19].

$$S = \frac{M \times L}{T}$$

Where ,

S= Spreadability

M= Mass

L=Diameter

T=Time.

Table No. 03 Spread-ability Readings for Formulation Batches.

Sr. No	Formulation	Length (cm)
1	F1	3.5
2	F2	4.00
3	F3	4.2
4	F4	3.5
5	F5	5.5
6	F6	5.0

9.Viscosity

The viscosity of emulgel was estimated using Brookfield viscometer. 1 gram of emulgel sample was taken. The spindle was rotated at the speed of 50 rpm. Readings were taken in triplicate and average of readings were calculated [20].

Table No. 04 Viscosity Readings for Formulation Batches.

Sr. No	Formulation	Viscosity (Pa.S)
1	F1	1701
2	F2	2125
3	F3	1259
4	F4	1582
5	F5	2110
6	F6	1830

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The leaf of Buchanania lanzan was collected and authenticated. The drug was dried and ground into a coarse powder. The powder was macerated for 48 hours using a hydroalcoholic solvent. The marc that was obtained was subjected to Soxhlet extraction. The extracts were combined and further concentrated. The extract obtained was used to study the phytochemical and physicochemical parameters.

The presence of alkaloids, tannins, carbohydrates, flavonoids, and terpenoids in the Buchanania lanzan leaf was determined by performing a phytochemical test. The results of the phytochemical analysis are presented in Table 4. Emulsion was prepared. Emulgel was prepared using different gelling agents like Carbopol-940, Sodium CMC and Sodium alginate. The concentration of gelling agent was decided on basis of review of literature. 6 formulations of emulgel were formulated. The prepared batches were evaluated for its colour, pH, Spreadability, viscosity and appearance.

The formulated batches had beige colour. The formulations F1, F3, F4 and F5 had good consistency whereas F2 and F6 had very good consistency. All the formulations were Washable.

Viscosity of formulations ranged from 1259-2125. The pH of formulation ranged from 6.00-6.68. Spreadability of formulations were found in range of 3.5 -5.5.

Table No. 05 Phytochemical parameters.

Test	Result
Alkaloids	+
Glycoside	+
Saponin	+
Steroids	-
Tannins	+
Flavonoids	+
Protein	-

Table No. 06 Post formulation studies.

	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Color	Brown	Brown	Brown	Brown	Brown	Brown
Consistency	Good	Very good	Good	Good	Good	Very good
Homogeneity	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good
Appearance	Semi-solid	Semi-solid	Semi-solid	Semi-solid	Semi-solid	Semi-solid
Greasiness	Non-greasy	Non-greasy	Non-greasy	Non-greasy	Non-greasy	Non-greasy
Washability	Washable	Washable	Washable	Washable	Washable	Washable
pH	6.22	6.68	6	6.03	6.17	6.03
Spreadability	3.5	4	4.2	3.5	5	5.5
Viscosity	1701	2125	1259	1582	2110	1830

Visuals of Formulation Batches

Fig. No. 01 Formulation batches (a).

Fig. No. 02 Formulation batches (b).

Fig. No. 03 PH Readings For all six formulations Batches.

Fig. No. 04 Spreadability for Formulations Batches.

Definitions/Abbreviations

1. LOD- Loss of Drying
2. Pa.s- Pascal Second

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